

Emotional Well being of Women Warfare in Higher Education - with Special Reference to Bourdieu Concepts

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: October

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Nithya, AR, and
Shahanaz Banu.

“Emotional Well being of Women Warfare in Higher Education - with Special Reference to Bourdieu Concepts.”
Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities,
vol. 7, no. S1, 2019,
pp. 95–110.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3549260>

Dr. A.R. Nithya

DoMS, Madurai Kamaraj University

Shahanaz Banu

MBA Student, DoMS, Madurai Kamaraj University

Introduction

Today’s competitive world is putting numerous challenges for the women development, the most noticeable facts are: recognition of the hard work that women in higher education do and the value of collaborative working for women in higher education. An African proverb goes: “If you educate a man you educate an individual, but if you educate a woman you educate a family (nation).” Education is a vital tool for bringing about gender parity and simultaneously catalysing national development. In this study our motto is about realising the sweats and struggles of the women pursuing higher education and even after completion what is level of recognition in the society. WHEN- Women in Higher Education Network, UK plays role in women development and their emotional well being. Despite the historical tradition of academia as a male space, there are now more women in higher education than ever before. Stephen Court, senior research officer at the AUT and author of *The Unequal Academy*, said: ‘The report reveals very different experiences of women and men working in higher education. Women may be flooding into universities but they do not appear to have the same opportunities as their male colleagues. This can be very demoralising’... ‘The more senior the grade, the lower proportion of female academics in the grade’...

In this study we focus about the warfare of women’s emotional well being in getting their higher education by adapting the Bourdieu concepts such as Emotional capital, Economic capital, Cultural capital. Emotional involvement in their higher education and serious thinking about their social stability, here emotional involvement refers to wide range of emotions both positive and negative. Here emotional capital is not coincide with emotional involvement but occupies a narrower conceptual range. His famous concept is cultural capital talks about ----

It is a relational concept and exists in relation with other forms of capital. All the other forms of capital such as emotional capital, economic capital are interrelated with cultural capital. Isolation focus about those things is not needed. Altogether with cultural capital constitute good and bad in the society. Economic capital talks about wealth either inherited or generated through interactions with the society. In addition to interconnection and their interdependent Bourdieu envisage about the transformation of one capital into other form.

Trigger for Our Study

It is observed fact that there is an increasing trend in female student enrolment at primary levels, which currently stands at 48% girls to 52% boys. Despite there is a huge drop-outs rate at the secondary level, at which point there is no compulsion from the state view about the higher education for the women. The more sensational fact is reduction in the female labour force i.e., from 34% to 27% in 2017. This decline trend indicates not only we should focus about education but quality education too. The Education 2030 agenda recognizes that gender equality requires an approach that 'ensures that girls and boys, women and men not only gain access to and complete education cycles, but are empowered equally in and through education.'

Review of Literature

Emotional well being is multi dimensional it is not a discipline, discourse alone but covering all these dimensions in ongoing relational practices (Burkitt, 1997:42) Providing women with quality education would break the existing hurdles to their employment, leading to the emergence of successful role models. The advent of these role models and leaders is critical for changing the perception of women in the community, particularly in areas where gender stereotypes are most entrenched. A corollary to this would be the improvement in self-esteem of girls, which would then enable them to actively challenge gender biases and achieve societal change. If we wish to create skilled, globalised, effective human capital based on a revived education system, we cannot afford to leave our girls behind.

Emotions are increasingly the focus of analysis across a number of disciplines and professional settings, including education (Schutz and Pekrun, 2007; Zembylas, 2005). Although emotions have largely been investigated through a range of scientific, biomedical and psychological discourses that consider emotional phenomena primarily as 'individual' and 'private' (Boler, 1999; Lupton, 1998), there is a growing effort to integrate these ideas with alternative views branching out into the sphere of culture and society (Ahmed, 2004; Lutz and Abu-Lughod, 1990; Williams, 2001). Historical and ethnographical work on emotions in the last decade show how emotions are experienced through social relations and culture, and thus are managed, not merely expressed, in interpersonal communication in conformity with collective social norms (Barbalet, 1998; Lupton, 1998; Reddy,²

In recent times, several social theorists assert that emotions are simultaneously signs for bodily states and cultural categories (Barbalet, 1998; Williams, 2001). While it is cultural categories that enable individuals to put embodied sensations into words and make them into emotions, the affective experiences that precede these cultural categories cannot be ignored (Lupton, 1998; Massumi, 2002). Thus, it is important to differentiate what is meant by the terms 'emotions' and 'affects' and briefly refer to the social formation of bodies. For this purpose, I turn to ethnographic work across cultures as well as theorisations of the embodied aspects of emotions (Leavitt, 1996; Thrift, 2004). In this literature, affect is defined as something first experienced in the body and then named and re-experienced through social relations and culture. According to this view, for example, the basic affects of anger, fear, disgust and so on are universal and embodied but cultural experiences and social interpretations of the embodiment of emotions allow much variation.

The concepts discussed such as emotional capital, cultural capital, economic capital has been developed from the work of Bourdieu who has invited researchers to develop his theoretical frame work in order to make sense of their empirical findings (Bourdieu 1990;107; Grenfell & James 1998) All the goods has its own economic value, but the goods which are scarce and availability hardship will create demand value in themarket, even it is applied in education also.

Bourdieu(1977, 1984, 1986) explains the ways in which capital functions with the help of various forms of capital such as economic, cultural and social- the togetherness and its differentiation will constitute imbalances in society particularly in educational sector. Economic capital refers to income and other financial resources, while cultural capital may take various forms, reflecting the modes of thinking, values, dispositions, sets of meaning and qualities of style that are primarily transmitted through the family. These qualities are assigned a particular social status in relation to what the dominant classes label as the most valued cultural capital (Giroux, 1983). Cultural capital can exist in three forms: embodied (dispositions of mind and body), objectified (cultural goods), and institutionalised (educational qualifications). Reay (2004a) and Skeggs (2004) argue for a broad understanding of cultural capital that also recognises its affective aspects such as levels of confidence and empowerment. Finally, social capital is generated through social processes and exists as social relations and networks (such as contacts and memberships). According to Bourdieu, these relationships and memberships add up to potential and actual resources that individuals can mobilise. It is the battle for distinction that gives social capital its qualities. Social capital constitutes then a useful emotional resource for individuals in their social relationships and thus includes certain norms and obligations that are maintained through rewards and punishments (cf. Halpern, 2005). What makes Bourdieu different from other theorists who also talk about social capital is his analysis of social capital as ubiquitous and continually transmitted (e.g. through community norms) and accumulated in ways that may reinforce existing social structures (Blackshaw and Long, 2005; Dika and Singh, 2002; Edward 2004).

Women Warfare in Higher Education

India's higher education system is the third largest after China and United states.As of 2019 India has 49 central universities, 367 state universities, 239 Deemed iuniversities and various institutes having national recognition such as IITs, IIMs and Universities such as JNU. Despite these numerous Institutes it is surprising fact the low presence of women record across most institutions for higher education., it may be seen that ratio of male is higher than female in almost every level, except M.Phil. and Post Graduate. Student enrolment at Under Graduate level has 51.9% male and 48.1% female. Diploma has a skewed distribution with 68% males and 32% females. Ph.D. level has 57.4% male and 42.6% female. Integrated levels have 58.4% male and 41.6% female. PG Diploma student enrolment is 54% for male students and 46% for female students.

Girls' and women's unequal access to, and performance in, education is both a cause and a result of multiple factors, including chronic and systemic gender-based discrimination reproduced in the education system. The over-emphasis on gender parity to measure progress has also led to unsatisfactory results in terms of girls and women's empowerment through education. The statistics do not show the many types of obstacles that girls and women face, not only in accessing but also in continuing education; nor do they tell much about the quality of learning processes and environment for girls and boys. The failure to analyse the situation through a gender lens has resulted in gender blind and ineffective policies that do little to correct gender inequalities.

The following surveyed report conveys authenticated data about female literacy in the various states of India, Among which Tamilnadu female literacy rate is 73.86% against male literacy rate of 86.81%

Survey Report

Sr. No.	State	Literacy Rate	Male Literacy Rate	Female Literacy
1	Andaman & Nicobar	86.27	90.11	81.84
2	Andhra Pradesh	67.4	75.56	59.74
3	Arunachal Pradesh	66.95	73.69	59.57
4	Assam	73.18	78.81	67.27
5	Bihar	63.62	73.39	53.33
6	Chandigarh	86.43	90.54	81.38
7	Chhattisgarh	71.04	81.45	60.59
8	Dadra & Nagar Haveli	77.55	86.46	65.93
9	Daman & Diu	87.07	91.48	79.59
10	Delhi	86.34	91.03	80.93
11	Goa	87.40	92.81	81.84
12	Gujarat	79.31	87.23	70.73
13	Haryana	76.64	85.38	66.77
14	Himachal Pradesh	83.78	90.83	76.60
15	Jammu & Kashmir	68.74	78.26	58.01
16	Jharkhand	67.63	78.45	56.21
17	Karnataka	75.60	82.85	68.13
18	Kerala	93.91	96.02	91.98
19	Lakshadweep	92.28	96.11	88.25
20	Madhya Pradesh	70.63	80.53	60.02
21	Maharashtra	82.91	89.82	75.48
22	Manipur	79.85	86.49	73.17
23	Meghalaya	75.48	77.17	73.78
24	Mizoram	91.58	93.72	89.40
25	Nagaland	80.11	83.29	75.89
26	Odisha	73.45	82.40	64.36
27	Puducherry	86.55	92.12	81.22
28	Punjab	76.68	81.48	71.34
29	Rajasthan	67.06	80.51	52.66
30	Sikkim	82.20	87.29	75.43
31	Tamil Nadu	80.33	86.81	73.86
32	Telangana	66.50	-	-
33	Tripura	87.75	92.18	83.15

34	Uttar Pradesh	69.72	79.24	59.26
35	Uttarakhand	79.63	88.33	70.70
36	West Bengal	77.08	82.67	71.16

Cultural Diversity, Women and Higher Education

Without doubt, the reality of cultural diversity is a most problematic area in relation to women as leaders and managers both in higher education and in society at large. Many factors come into play - the historical roles of women in certain societies, the conflicts arising from their advanced education and exposure to other cultures, their own continued commitment to the values of their own race, religion and nation.

The Main Problems Facing their Education are

- Development of immorality;
- Suitable Curriculum for the education of girls;
- Lack of social consciousness among women;
- Scarcity of lady teachers;
- Lack of proper physical facilities;
- Unwillingness of lady teachers to serve in rural areas;
- Financial difficulties;
- Problem of transport;
- Problem of wastage and stagnation;
- Problem of co-education;
- Lack of enthusiasm and interest of the officials in charge of education

The education of girls and women is an integral part of national development. Steps that are being taken to improve and expand their education will not recede to the background due to lack of finance. It must be remembered that there is still a big gap to be filled between the education of the boys and girls, further; mother is the pivot of family life in India. Our way of life depends on her. It is essential; therefore, that at least the programmes for girls and women that have already been included in the current plan are not disturbed.

Domestic Duty

Many societies and a vast population in India still believes that proper place for women is to remain at home, serve the husband and his family and give birth to the children. This function can be performed irrespective of the fact whether the girl is educated or not. In fact, they feel that educated women begin to get some enlightens and start demanding. Especially in a poor section of the society they are required in bring potable water, take food to fields for parents engaged in work and look after their young siblings, besides some are required to work as paid and unpaid workers.

Social Factors

The marriage of girls is a determining factor in women education. Particularly early marriage in UP, MP, Bihar, Rajasthan and Gujarat has been responsible for depriving girls from attending classes. Millions of literate girls are given a way in marriage even before they are in their teens. Today, however, early marriage is not so common and women education has been encouraged by its increasing demand in their marriage markets especially among the upper and middle classes. Thus due to socio-economical reasons, women in India are still not coming in as much in number in the educational institution. The task ahead is difficult. The very fact is also that education among women education in urban India is widespread and more and more number of women is going to school and colleges.

Conservation Mentality

In India, women education has been linked with employment. In other words, the children are educated simply because they are to get some employment. Those people who are not in favour of sending their daughter for employment do not feel the necessity of educating them.

Lack of Girls School or Co-educational Aspects

The numbers of women's educational institutions is much less as compared with institutions engage education in the spread of male education. Therefore in many cases, particularly in remote the village the women are supposed to travel some distance, before reaching an women education institution. Many people do not like that their daughter should leave the village for going to school. Many people still condemn and dislike the idea of co-education. They feel that when both boys and girls study together in a same educational institution, corruption is bound to breed. They, therefore, are not prepared to send their daughter to a co-education institution.

Non-availability of a school within walking distance of the girls, particularly in backward areas and the unwillingness of many parents to send their daughter to mixed schools beyond the age of 9 plus. Lack of separate sanitary facilities for girls in the mixed schools and lack of suitable school buildings and equipment which tend to create a poor school environment and the crisis of no of girls' hostel in near the schools.

Lack of Women Teachers for Women Education in India

The lack of women teachers in primary and middle schools has been very largely responsible for the low enrolment of girls, especially in the nine backward states. It is an accepted fact that the primary schools should be staffed by women teachers. At present the proportion of women teachers to men teachers is very low.

Lack of Supervision and Personal Guidance for Women Education

The development of women education in the different States have been seriously hampered because of the inadequate machinery to look after the various programmes in this field which require concentrated attention, special care and individual guidance. The number of lady officers is far too small to shoulder the responsibility of speeding of the progress of women education as envisaged in our plan. The officers are poorly staffed and ill-equipped. They do not have suitable conveyance facilities which would help in maintaining regular contacts within their field of work.

Lack of Adequate Incentives for Women Education

The poor enrolment position of girls, especially in backward areas, cannot be improved unless special incentives are provided. Special schemes sponsored by the government of India have been adopted in several states. Although the schemes have been implemented, they do not cover a very wide area and the total results thus fall short of expectation. In order to ensure that these special schemes provide adequate incentives to the students, it is necessary that they are adopted in larger measures and over a wider geographical area with special priority to the backward districts or pockets.

Initiatives by the Government

In recent times, from BetiBachao, BetiPadhao to Sukanya Samridhi Yojana, the government has taken several enabling, affirmative actions. Initiatives like distribution of bicycles to girls to tackle concerns regarding safety and improvement in infrastructure by adding usable toilets enhances retention of girls at schools.

Digital platforms can also be used to augment access to education and can be delivered through our gram panchayat and rural development systems that are already in place, thereby ensuring access to education for women across India. It is expected that, by June 2018, there will be 500 million internet users in the country, with 87% reach in rural areas. E-learning can be the technological vehicle for women’s groups to handle issues around health, hygiene, child bearing and other information they rarely have access to.

In dealing with the tension between women of varied cultures and their role in the advancement of higher education, several points must be kept in mind:

- strong record of academic leadership/excellence in research and teaching
- leadership skills, including visioning capacities
- management skills
- institutional experience
- international experience of higher education
- negotiating skills to deal with all stakeholders (internally, the management, the professoriate and students; externally, national policy-makers, the economic sector, community groups, regional and international peer groups)
- communication skills including, if possible, charisma.

As the challenges facing higher education grow more complex, it is true that the governance of this sector requires even greater skills. And, these challenges come at a time when top leadership itself is under close scrutiny.

Research Methodology

In this study Qualitative research was conducted for analyzing the perceptions and view of the women candidates those who pursuing higher education in Madurai Kamaraj University using descriptive research design type. Simple random sampling method was used. Sample size is, 50

Statistical tool used percentage analysis, weighted average analysis, frequency analysis, regression analysis test, H- test, U-test.

Analysis and Findings

Demographic Variable

Demographic Variables	Parameters	Frequency	Percentage Analysis
Age	20-22	41	82
	23-24	9	18
Under Graduation	Arts	32	62.7
	Science	17	33.3
	Engineering	2	3.9
Family Type	Joint Family	11	21.6
	Nuclear	38	74.5
Marital Status	Married	3	5.9
	Unmarried	48	94.1
Parental Monthly Income	< Rs.20,000	28	54.9
	Rs. 20,000 - 25,000	11	21.6
	Rs. 25,000 - 30,000	4	7.8
	Rs. 30,000 - 35,000	3	5.9
	More than Rs. 35,000	5	9.8

National Seminar on **Role of Women in Higher Education**

Number of Siblings	1	28	54.9
	2	15	29.4
	More than 2	5	9.8
	No Siblings	3	5.9
Parental Occupation - Father	Government Employee	8	15.7
	Private	26	51.0
	Entrepreneur	4	7.8
	Agriculturists	9	17.6
	Unemployed	4	7.8
Parental Occupation - Mother	Government Employee	2	3.9
	Private	5	9.8
	Entrepreneur	2	3.9
	Agriculturists	1	2.0
	Unemployed	41	80.4

Weighted Average Analysis

Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
SCF - In our country, higher education is meant for men alone	51	1	5	2.49	1.461	.481	.333
Marriage is a factor that decides about higher education	51	1	5	3.08	1.481	-.063	.333
Attitude about traditional culture affects my education	51	1	5	3.06	1.240	-.050	.333
Talking to/ Working with men is strictly prohibited	51	1	5	2.96	1.341	-.340	.333
Being a women, I lose opportunities due to my family constraints	51	1	5	2.92	1.468	-.057	.333
Generally, higher education is not permitted	51	1	5	2.31	1.334	.655	.333
My skill development is comparatively less preferential than my safety	51	1	5	2.96	1.095	.271	.333
Safety is a biggest concern that affects my higher education	51	1	5	3.00	1.265	.000	.333
Value of women life is under-estimated	51	1	5	3.00	1.356	.000	.333

Male is having moral responsibility in taking care of the family, comparing to women in the family	51	1	5	2.90	1.204	-.091	.333
Religious significance is meant for male education in family	51	1	5	2.71	1.432	.289	.333
Lacking of religious charity support for women	51	1	5	3.08	1.197	-.447	.333
Due to the effect of poverty, my education is less preferred one	51	1	5	2.76	1.380	-.033	.333
Menstrual pain and other health issues adversely affect my education	51	1	5	2.94	1.363	.160	.333
Men in the family gets preferential food compared to women in the family	51	1	5	3.00	1.356	-.100	.333
Valid N (listwise)	51						

Interpretation

From the above data analysis using weighted average it is found that the most influencing variable is ‘Marriage is a factor that decides about higher education, Lacking of religious charity support for women’, these two variables are the most influencing variable for Socio – Cultural factor deciding the women education.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Due to the effect of poverty, my education is less preferred one	51	1	5	2.76	1.380
Cost of education affects my higher education	51	1	5	3.00	1.371
Patriarchal factors/ Male dominants affect my investment in education	51	1	5	2.73	1.372
Investment for women school education is waste	51	1	5	2.67	1.633
Avoidance of buying books, uniforms may affect the women educational growth	51	1	5	2.88	1.381
Status of women is not considered in society	51	1	5	2.90	1.285
Education for women is not a value added to the family	51	1	5	2.61	1.401
Female education is disenchantment	51	1	5	2.73	1.201
My family does not allows me to go for long distance for my education	51	1	5	3.04	1.356
Sometimes distance disturbs my education	51	1	5	2.94	1.377
The location of the institution is a key factor for deciding my education	51	1	5	3.20	1.281
Being a women, I feel disparity in my family	51	1	5	2.80	1.281
Valid N (listwise)	51				

Interpretation

From the above analysis, it is found that the most influencing variable is ‘The location of the institution is a key factor for deciding women education and Their family does not allows them to go for long distance for their higher education’, these two variables are the most influencing variable for Economic factor deciding about the women education.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Safety is a biggest concern in considering the women higher education	51	1	5	3.12	1.336
Educational breakage is common in women	51	1	5	3.06	1.103
Location of institution becomes hindrance for women higher education	51	1	5	3.37	1.095
Goodwill of the study centre is a important concern	51	1	5	3.47	1.376
Reputation of the faculty decides the future of the education	51	1	5	2.86	1.233
Lack of female teachers in higher education sector	51	1	5	2.65	1.197
Timings of the study centre concerns about the continuation of higher education	51	1	5	3.14	1.217
Vocational/ Enterpreunel studies are lagging for women in higher education	51	1	5	3.00	1.077
Valid N (listwise)	51				

Interpretation

From the above data analysis, it is found that the most influencing variable is ‘Goodwill of the study centre is a important concern, Location of the institution becomes hindrance for women higher education’, these two variables are the most influencing variable for Educational factor deciding the women education.

Kruskal Wallis test(H test)

Ranks			
Marriage is a factor that decides about higher education	Under Graduation	N	Mean Rank
	Arts	32	27.38
	Science	17	23.47
	Engineering	2	25.50
	Total	51	

Test Statistics a,b	
	Marriage is a factor that decides about higher education
Chi-Square	.803
df	2
Asymp. Sig.	.669
a. Kruskal Wallis Test	
b. Grouping Variable: Under Graduation	

Interpretation

In the above H- Test we have taken the variables 'Under Graduation' of the respondent and factor variable is 'Marriage is a factor that decides about higher education', Since the P value is 0.669 which is more than 0.05, we conclude that null hypothesis is accepted, that is there is no significant relationship between the Under graduation and the cultural factor that is 'Marriage is a factor that decides about higher education'.

ANOVA						
	Cluster	Error	F	Sig.		
	Mean Square	Df	Mean Square	df		
Cost of education affects my higher education	25.205	1	1.404	49	17.952	.000
Patriarchal factors/ Male dominants affect my investment in education	18.867	1	1.537	49	12.279	.001
Investment for women school education is waste	30.729	1	2.094	49	14.675	.000
Avoidance of buying books, uniforms may affect the women educational growth	18.337	1	1.571	49	11.675	.001
Status of women is not considered in society	12.734	1	1.424	49	8.942	.004
Education for women is not a value added to the family	23.624	1	1.521	49	15.531	.000
Female education is disenchantment	13.809	1	1.191	49	11.597	.001
My family does not allows me to go for long distance for my education	20.561	1	1.456	49	14.118	.000
Sometimes distance disturbs my education	34.885	1	1.223	49	28.519	.000
The location of the institution is a key factor for deciding my education	.155	1	1.671	49	.093	.762
Being a women, I feel disparity in my family	18.601	1	1.295	49	14.367	.000

The F tests should be used only for descriptive purposes because the clusters have been chosen to maximize the differences among cases in different clusters. The observed significance levels are not corrected for this and thus cannot be interpreted as tests of the hypothesis that the cluster means are equal.

Interpretation

From the above F- Test, it is found that 'Distance' and 'Cost of education affects my higher education' are those variables which are having the significant differential relationship in women education.

Chi Square test

Hypothesis Tested: There is a significant relationship between under graduation undergone by the respondents and parental monthly income

Under Graduation * Parental Monthly Income Crosstabulation							
Count							
	Parental Monthly Income						Total
	< Rs.20,000	Rs. 20,000 - 25,000	Rs. 25,000 - 30,000	Rs. 30,000 - 35,000	More than Rs. 35,000		

Under Graduation	Arts	18	10	1	0	3	32
	Science	9	1	3	2	2	17
	Engineering	1	0	0	1	0	2
Total	28	11	4	3	5	51	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.710a	8	.033
Likelihood Ratio	15.387	8	.052
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.802	1	.179
N of Valid Cases	51		

a. 12 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

Interpretation

As P value is less than 0.05, null hypothesis can be rejected. There is a significant relationship between their under graduation and parental income.

Regression Analysis

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.629a	.395	.313	1.106

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Goodwill of the study center is a important concern, Lacking of religious charity support for women, My family does not allows me to go for long distance for my education, Location of institution becomes hindrance for women higher education, The location of the institution is a key factor for deciding my education, Marriage is a factor that decides about higher education
- b. Dependent Variable: Generally, higher education is not permitted

Interpretation

In the above regression analysis, from the table of correlation it is found that the R value is 0.629 which indicates the highly positive correlation between the variables.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	35.176	6	5.863	4.794	.001 ^b
	Residual	53.805	44	1.223		
	Total	88.980	50			

- a. Dependent Variable: Generally, higher education is not permitted
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Goodwill of the study center is a important concern, Lacking of religious charity support for women, My family does not allows me to go for long distance for my education, Location of institution becomes hindrance for women higher education, The location of the institution is a key factor for deciding my education, Marriage is a factor that decides about higher education

Interpretation

From the above table it is found that the F value is 4.794 and its associated P value is 0.001 which is less than 0.05 that indicates that there is a significant relation between the dependent variable and its associated independent variable.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.103	.704		-.146	.884
	Marriage is a factor that decides about higher education	.114	.127	.127	.899	.374
	Lacking of religious charity support for women	.341	.145	.306	2.357	.023
	My family does not allows me to go for long distance for my education	.486	.141	.494	3.453	.001
	The location of the institution is a key factor for deciding my education	-.266	.142	-.256	-1.872	.068
	Location of institution becomes hindrance for women higher education	.042	.166	.035	.255	.800
	Goodwill of the study center is a important concern	.071	.125	.074	.572	.570

a. Dependent Variable: Generally, higher education is not permitted

Interpretation

From the above regression table, it is found that the most significant variable is ‘Women family does not allow them to go for long distance for their education(X1), Lacking of religious charity support for women (X2)’ are the most influencing variables for the women higher education. $Y(\text{Permission for Women Higher Education})=X1+X2$: (Women family does not allow them to go for long distance for their education(X1), Lacking of religious charity support for women (X2)

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.710a	8	.033
Likelihood Ratio	15.387	8	.052
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.802	1	.179
N of Valid Cases	51		

a. 12 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

Test Applied-Mann Whitney U test

Hypothesis tested	P Values	Result
There is no significant relationship between marital status and Marriage is a factor that decides higher education	1.187	Null hypothesis accepted

There is no significant relationship between Goodwill of the study centre is a important concern and the family type	0.469	Null hypothesis accepted
There is no significant relationship between Location of institution becomes hindrance for women higher education and family type	0.642	Null hypothesis accepted
There is no significant relationship between Attitude about traditional culture affects my education and family type	0.02	Null hypothesis rejected
There is no significant relationship between Timings of the study centre concerns about the continuation of higher education and family type	0.03	Null hypothesis rejected

Findings of the Study

From the above study we have found that

- Maximum respondents are belonging to the age of 20 – 22 years,
- Most of the respondents are from the Arts background
- 75% of the respondents belonging to Nuclear Family
- Marital status of most of the respondents are Unmarried
- Most of the respondents belongs to the family category of less than Rs. 20000, Hence most of the parental income rely on the middle income group
- Majority of the respondents having only one sibling
- Majority of the respondents Parental Income of the Father are from Private company.
- 80% of the respondents Mother are homemaker(Unemployed).

From the tools applied

- By applying weighted average analysis, we found that marriage is a factor that decides about the higher education
- Two factors influence the women education:
 - Marriage is a factor that decides about higher education and
 - Lacking of charity support for women education

Women Marriage is also a factor that may decides about her higher education, Normally, people from middle income background they want an early settlement for their female child, in that case for the security and safety of women they prefer marriage as a way for settling them.

Most of the women opines that lack of their religious charity support for their education, that is there is no such option for their higher education which also may become a factor in hindrance of the women education.

- The location of the institution is the highly influencing variable in economic factor, most of the families does not want their ward to send at a distant travel for higher education as for as safety and transportation cost is also concerned about the location of the institution.
- Goodwill of the institution is a maximum influencing variable in educational factor, if the study centre does not possess any bad fame, people will have strong belief about the reputation of the institution. Thus, Goodwill of the institution plays a vital role in educational factors in deciding women education.
- By applying H – test, variables measured are
 - Marriage is a factor that decides about higher education and their
 - Under Graduation

From this test we found that, under graduation does not have much impact in the higher education whereas Marriage is a only factor that has influence upon women higher education.

- By applying ANOVA analysis we found that two variables having maximum significant differential relation in the women education

- Distance of the education and
- Cost of the education
- Distance and cost of education makes the family to decide about the higher education for women.
- By applying Chi- Square for the variables, UG and the respondents Parental Monthly Income, there is a significant differential relation between them. When the parental monthly income is more than that of middle level then there is no hindrance for the education of the women.
- By applying regression analysis, we found that weighted average analysis is proved in this regression test, that is the variables location of the institution and lacking of charity support for women education are the highly influencing variables in the women higher education.
- By applying Mann Whitney test, most of the variables shows that there is no significant relationship. But while measuring the family type with the location of the institution, there is no family type role in deciding the distance of the education. The variable 'Attitude about the traditional culture affects their education' is accepted. That is most of the families having their attitude as women can be limited for UG, pursuing higher education is a additional cost and time consumed, these are the reasons for less preferencing the higher education.
- Timing of the study centre is also an influencing variable in the women higher education.

Suggestions and Conclusion

From our study we can conclude that there are so many factors that play a vital role in affecting women higher education.

- As per the Socio – Cultural capital factor, Marriage is a main factor that affects the higher education and Lack of religious charity support for the women education.
- Economic capital factor, Cost of education and location of the institution are these factors that adversely affect the women higher education.
- For improving the women education, we have to provide the awareness about the women leadership to the family members also to the society.
- 'A women is Educated, A Society is Educated, A Family is Educated', So we have to inculcate the importance of women education in the society.
- Among the initiatives taken by the Government the most important one is Women Education. As per 'BetiBachao' scheme, our Prime Minister insist of having a female child in the family. Having a female child is an pride for the family and also providing proper education that might enlighten the lives of the female.
- We can conclude that by providing awareness to the people about women education, we can eradicate the above mentioned factors.
- Women with economic empowerment will be a suitable one for the marriage. Charity support from various religious organisation for women higher education, so far there is no religious support for women particularly for higher education. These factors can be taken into consideration. Also if there is also an additional financial support from other organisation, the cost of the higher education and the location of the institution will become a minor impact in the women higher education

Bibliography

1. <https://mhrd.gov.in>
2. <http://www.pincodeindia.net/literacy-rate.php>
3. <http://www.aishe.org>

National Seminar on **Role of Women in Higher Education**

4. A Blueprint for Leadership. Office of Women in higher Education, American Council on Education, Washington, 1994.
5. Bond, Sheryl. Service and self-respect: Women Leaders in Latin American Universities. UNESCO, 1997.
6. Education: a Means for Empowering Girls and Women. UNESCO, Paris, 1994.
7. Higher Education and Capacity-building for the 21st Century. Report of the 4th UNESCO/ NGO Collective Consultation on Higher Education. UNESCO, Paris, 1995.
8. Higher Education: The Lessons of Experience. World Bank, 1994.
9. La Responsabilité des femmes dans la conduite de leur carrière et enseignements supérieurs. Rapport de la Table Ronde UNESCO/FIFDU, 1988.
10. Social Development, Women and Higher Education. UNESCO/IFUW Submission to the Commission on Education for the XXI Century, UNESCO, 1994.
11. The World Education Report. UNESCO, Paris, 1995, 1996.
12. Women Graduates and the Labour Market. 5th NGO Collective Consultation on Higher Education, Volume 3, UNESCO, 1997.